

THE DESCRIPTION OF THE TOPONYMY OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE WORK “HUDUD UL-OLAM”

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Annotation: This article provides an analysis of the work "Hudud ul-olam" and its sections, the scientific foundations of this work in the works of scientists, and a detailed description of the geographical, ethnographic, economic and toponomic names of the territory of Uzbekistan in the work.

Keywords: work, historical - geographical work, nature, people, customs, people, region, city, country, toponymy, sector, center, manuscript, valley.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada “Hudud ul-olam” asari va uning bo‘limlari tahlili, olimlarning asarlarida mazkur asar haqidagi ilmiy asoslari, asarda O‘zbekiston hududining geografik, etnografik, iqtisodiy hamda toponomik nomlari haqita batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: asar, tarixiy – geografik asar, tabiat, xalq, urf-odat, inson, viloyat, shahar, mamlakat, toponomiya, tarmoq, markaz, qo‘lyozma, vodi.

Аннотация: В статье дается подробный анализ произведения “Худуд ул-Олам” и его разделов, научных основ этого произведения в трудах ученых, а также географических, этнографических, экономических и топонимических названий территории Узбекистана в работа.

Ключевые слова: труд, историко-географический труд, природа, народ, обычаи, человек, регион, город, страна, топонимика, сеть, центр, рукопись, долина.

“Khudud ul-Olam” is a historical and geographical work written in 982-983 in the Persian-Tadjik language by an unknown author. The work provides information about the climate, nature, peoples, customs, and occupations of the countries in the inhabited (one-quarter) part of the Earth’s surface. The manuscript was found in 1892 by the translator Abulfazl Gulpayogani in Bukhara. In 1893, he gave it to the orientalist A. Tumansky. V. Bartol’d published the text of “Khudud ul-Olam” with a preface and annotations in Russian, and in 1937, the Russian orientalist V. Minorsky published it in English.

Professor Kh. Khasanov wrote a large article about “Khudud ul-Olam” in his book “Central Asian Geographer and Traveler” and provided an Uzbek translation of many parts.[1] You can get an idea of the content of “Khudud ul-Olam” and the names of its numbered sections: Introduction, the boundaries, beauty and ruins of the earth, seas and bays, islands (peninsula), mountains and their minerals, rivers, deserts and sands (deserts and marshes), world regions

(regions of the world), characteristics of the Chinese region, Indian region, Tibet region and its cities, Toguz-Guz region and its cities, yagmo region and its cities, kyrgyz region, khalukh region and its cities, jikil region, tukhsi region and its cities, kimok region and its cities, guz region, bayjonaki turk region, khipchak region, majghari region, Khurasan region and its cities, Khurasan outskirts and its cities, Mavoraunnakhr province and its cities, Mavoraunnakhr suburbs and its cities, Sindh province and its cities, Kerman province and its cities, Bors (Persia) province and its cities, Jibal province and its cities, Khuzestan province and its cities, Daylamon province and its cities, Irak province and its cities, Jazira province and its cities, Azerbaijan province and Armenia and Arran province, Arab province and its cities, Shorn province and its cities, Egypt province and its cities, Maghreb province and its cities, Andalusia province and its cities, Rum region and its cities, Sakalob region, Rus region and its cities, Inner Bulgar region, Mirvat region, Bajanoki Khazar region, Alan region and its cities, Sarir region and its cities, Khazar region, Barados region, Burtos region, Vanandar region, Southern developed lands and regions, Zangistan region and its cities, Zobaj region and its cities, Habasha region and its cities, Buja region, Nuba region, Sudan region and its cities, end of the book.[2]

As can be seen from the table of contents, “Khudud ul-Olam” is a geographical, ethnographic and economic reference book that describes all the countries of the world. The fact that the work was written in Persian indicates that the local Persian-Tajik culture was quite high at that time (10th century). Let us dwell on some geographical names in “Khudud ul-Olam”. The mountains of Movaraunnakhr.

According to Kh. Khasanov, “Khudud ul-Olam” includes the mountains of Bulur, Samarkand, Shiknon, that is, Khan Vakon in the south of Central Asia. The Ustrushona, Khuttalon, Chaghaniyon mountains, which are located inside Buttamon and spread to Movaraunnakhr, and their branches are described in detail. [3] Then, many mountain branches in Movaraunnakhr are described by name. From the table of contents, it can be seen that “Khudud ul-Olam” is a geographical, ethnographic and economic reference book that describes all the countries of the world.

The fact that the work was written in Persian indicates that the local Persian-Tajik culture was quite high at that time (10th century). Let us dwell on some geographical names in “Khudud ul-Olam”. Mountains of Movaraunnakhr. According to Kh. Khasanov, “Khudud ul-Olam” describes the mountains of Bo'lur, Samarkand, Shiknon, that is, Khan Vakon in the south of Central Asia. The

mountains of Ustrushon, Khuttalon, Chaghaniyon, which are located inside Buttamon and spread to Movarounnakhr, and their branches are described in detail. Then many mountain branches in Movarounnakhr are described without names. Rivers of Movarounnakhr.[4]

“The Jaykhun (Amu) River flows from the Vahon region and passes between the Bomir (Pamir) region and Shignoni Vahon region, and flows into the Khorezm Sea”. “...The Hamab (Panj) flows from the west of the Kasark mountain and passes between Badakhshan and Porgar (Parkhor) and joins the Jaykhun” another river.

It is called Vakhshob, it rises from the Vakhsh mountains, flows into the Jaykhun near the Vakhsh (city).” “The Chaghonrud (Surkhandarya), which flows from Chaghaniyan and flows into the Jaykhun near Termez.” “...The other is the Uzgand water, which starts from the (back) of the Hallukh mountain, passes by the cities of Uzgand, Bab (Pop), Akhsikat, Khujand, Banokat and reaches the lands of Chach, and then flows into the Khorezm Sea.” So, the author probably means the Sirdaryo as the water of Uzgand and the Khalukh mountain is probably the Tien Shan mountains (in the early Middle Ages there was a karluq state in Yettisuv).

The current village of Akhsi (Namangan region, Turakurgan district) was a large city in the Middle Ages and was considered the center of the Ferghana valley. The center of the current Pop district is the city of Pop.[5] The city, which Banokat Amir Temur rebuilt in 1392 and named after his eldest son, Shahrukh Mirza, gradually became Sharkiya in the vernacular. One branch of the Ahangaran river is still called Sharkiya.

The ruins of the city are located in the territory of the Akkurgan district of the Tashkent region. “Another river (the current Kurshab river) is Khurshab, from the outskirts of Buttamon. “begins in the northern mountains and flows into the Uzgand (Syr Darya) near the city of Khurshab” . “Another is the Chach River. It flows into the Uzgand”. “Another river is the Kuba (water), which flows into the Uzgand (water) near the city of Kuba”. Kuba is the Kuva stream and the city of Kuva in the Ferghana region. In “Khudud ul-Alam” the Naryn river is called Khatlom after the city of Khatlom. Another is the Parak River. It passes through the lands of Chach. It flows into the Uzgand.

After all these rivers are joined, the whole water is called the Chach River, the Arabs (taziyon) call this river Saykhun. Parak is the Chirchik river. So, the headwaters were Uzgand, and after Chirchik was drained, the Syrdarya was called the Chach river. In the work “Khudud ul-Olam” Zarafshan is called the

Bukhara River. From this information it can be seen that rivers were often named after cities or regions. Vakhsh river - the city of Vakhsh. Chaghonrud (Chaghoniyon). Uzgand water - the city of Uzgand, Khurshab river - the city of Khurshab. Khatlom river - the city of Khatlom, Chach river - Chach (city, region), Osh river - the city of Osh. The author of "Khudud ul-Olam" once called the Syrdarya Hasart. Based on this, Kh. Khasanov draws the following conclusion: "It turns out that in the 10th century the Syrdarya was called Uzgand and Hasart on the territory of Uzbekistan. Thus, Hasart is one of the local names, and the form of Yaksart written in the books of the ancient Greeks was probably taken from then with some changes". "Movaraunnakhr is a vast, prosperous and very beautiful country.

It is the gate of Turkestan and a place of merchants". The cities and some regions of Uzbekistan are described in the work as follows: " Bukhara is a great city, the most prosperous city of Movarunnakhr". " Paykend is a small town with about a hundred rabots (in Narshakhi's "History of Bukhara" more than a thousand rabots)". (The ruins of the early medieval city known as Paykend, Baykand, Poykand are located in the southwestern outskirts of Bukhara).[6] "Karmina, Dabusi, Arbinjon are among the smaller cities of Sughd. Kushoniya is one of the most prosperous cities of Sughd..." . "Samarkand is a great, prosperous and very rich city. Merchants from all over the world come here..." . "Kesh is one of the cities of the hot region. There is a lot of rainfall there..." . "Termez is one of the prosperous cities on the banks of the Jaykhun. This city is the trading center of Khatlon and Chaghaniyan..." . "Chaghaniyoli is a convenient and spacious place for agriculture and cattle breeding, but its people are very few." "The capital of these regions is the city of Chaghaniyan, built at the foot of the mountain". "Dizak is a small city, on the water..." . "Ferghana is a great, prosperous and very beautiful region. It has mountains, plains, many running waters and cities..." . "Chatgal (Chatkol) is part of Ferghana.

It is located among the mountains. There are many small towns and villages. Horses and sheep are grazed, there are also mines" . "Akhsikat is the capital of Ferghana, the residence of the emir. This is a large city, on the banks of the Hasart River (Syr Darya). "Sokh is between the mountains. A place on the border of Buttamon and Ferghana, there are 60 villages" . "Kibo (Kuva) is the most prosperous large city of Ferghana..." . "Shosh is a large and prosperous, beautiful place. The capital of Shosh is Binkat". "Kot is the capital of Khorezm... This city is a trading center for Turks, Turkestan, Movaraunnakhr and Hazam. Its ruler is called the Khorezm Shah".

In general, in the work “Khudud ul-Olam” you can get a lot of information about Movaraunnakhr. In particular, the geography of Uzbekistan, especially its ancient toponymy.

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